

SIMILAR FEATURES AND SEMANTIC MEANINGS OF PAREMIAS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES.

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ABSTRACT In the article the usage of paremias in interpersonal relations, exchange of ideas as well as studying proverbs and sayings from a linguistic and cultural point of view is described. Additionally, this article analyzes the comparison of paremias expressing similar semantic meanings and interpersonal relations in English and Uzbek languages.

ANNOTATSIYA Ushbu maqolada paremiyalarning shaxslararo munosabatlar, fikr almashishda qo'llanilishi, shuningdek, maqollar va hikmatli so'zlarni lingvistik hamda madaniy nuqtayi nazardan tadqiqi yoritilgan. Bundan tashqari, maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tillarida o'xshash ma'nolarni anglatuvchi va shaxslararo munosabatlar ifodalovchi paremiyalarning qiyoslanishi tahlil qilingan.

Keywords: paremia, paremiology, proverb, saying, culture, equivalent.

Introduction. Proverbs and sayings reflect the nation's experience as well as every day, social, historical, and spiritual ideas that are essential to this people. Due to their direct relationship to people's lives and historical events, proverbs are frequently evaluative and have implications that emerge based on people's experiences. Paremias being vital part of culture are considered one of the most significant issues of linguistics in all languages as well as in English and Uzbek. Basically, the study of proverbs is called paremiology (from Greek παροιμία - paroimía, "proverb").

Literature review. The Greek word "paremia" which means "wise thought"

include proverbs and sayings that generalize various phenomena of the reality around us, help to understand the history of each nation.

A.N. Afanasev, A.A. Potebnya, N.V. Kryuchkova, G.V. Kolshansky, F.I. Buslaev, K.I. Grigas, G.L. Permyakov, A. Dandis, H. Casares, V.V. Gvozdev, Yu.I. Levin, G.N. Kurbatsky, Sh.S. Chadamba, and V.P. Zhukov's works as well as textbooks on oral folk art, the Russian literary language, collections of proverbs and sayings by A.M. Zhiguleva, V.I. Dahl, Yu.G. Kruglov and others, dictionaries and reference books according to the study of paremias shared a great deal in the progress of the domain.

There have been continuous development in the study of paremias in linguistics all the time. However, there are still a lot of controversial issues left to be focused on as the paremiological units from both cultural and linguistic point of view are gaining true importance these days. Regarding this issue, V.A. Maslova writes: Traditionally, proverbs were studied as a genre in folklore. Their studies in linguistics are just beginning. From a pragmatic point of view, the purpose of proverbs is ambiguous: the same proverb can be a rebuke, consolation, moral education, advice, threat, etc., for example: "Old age is not joy"¹.

Proverbs and sayings reflect the rich historical experience of the people, ideas related to work, life and culture of people. The correct and appropriate use of proverbs and sayings gives speech a unique originality and special expressiveness. Frequently, the words used in paremias mean completely different meanings when separated, therefore, it makes the study of proverbs even more crucial in order to comprehend the message that paremias intend to deliver.

Research methodology. Proverbs in all nations, basically, address moral issues and carry advisable messages. It is obviously the best way to find equivalents of them in order to deliver the very meaning of the proverbs from the

¹ Maslova A.V. Linguoculturology. - M. Academy, 2001, pp. 42-43.

source language into the target language. There are equivalents of English proverbs in Uzbek language about some particular abstract notions. Common features and similar meanings of proverbs are explained through qualitative method in this article.

Research materials. Uzbek proverbial dictionaries, mainly, O‘zbek xalq maqollari.[Uzbek people proverbs] was compiled T.Mirzayev , A.Musoqulov & B.Sarimsoqov and Oxford Dictionary of Proverbs (6 ed.) which was compiled by J.Speake and published in 2015 are the most used sources while writing the article.

Analysis and results. There are some examples that paremias of both languages share common features and similar semantic meanings:

About friendship: “Books are our best friends” – “Kitob bizning do‘stimiz”; “A friend in need is a friend indeed” - “Do‘st kulfatda bilinar”- A friend that sticks with you and helps you when you’re in trouble is a true friend.

“False friends are worse than open enemies” – “Soxta do‘st yovdan yomon” - It’s better to at least know who your enemy is, instead of believing someone is your friend only to find out that they aren’t. At least when you know who your enemy is, you know not to trust them.

About love, affection: “Love is blind” – “Muhabbatning ko‘zi ko‘r”; “Love knows no boundaries” – “Muhabbat chegara bilmas”;

Greed and stinginess, avarice: “When all other sins are old, greed still stays young.” – “Sochlar, tishlar, quloqlar qariydi - faqat ochko‘zlik qarimaydi.” “Bo‘rining o‘zi to‘ysa ham ko‘zi to‘ymaydi” - "Eyes are bigger than one's stomach". "Five hands do not fit in the mouth" – “Besh barmoq og‘iz yirtar”; "Grasp all, lose all." This proverb is said to greedy people, meaning that there is a measure for everything.

About patience and impatience: “Patience is bitter but its fruits are sweet.” – “Sabr, sabrning tagi sariq oltin”; “Jo‘jani kuzda sanaymiz” – “Chickens are

counted in autumn”; “Gul tikansiz bo’lmas, dur – sadafsiz” – “No rose without a thorn”; “Sabr tagi sariq oltin” – “Everything comes to him who waits”; “Har yerni qilma orzu har yerda bor tosh-u tarozi” – “In every country the sun rises in the morning”.

About hard work and strive: “Sendan harakat mendan barakat” – “God helps those who helps themselves”; “Hechdan ko’ra kech yaxshi” – “Better late than never”; “Uyqu - g’afolat, mehnat – rohat” – “The tortoise wins the race while the hare is sleeping”; “Mehnat, mehnatning tagi rohat” – “No pains no gains”. “Gul tikansiz bo’lmas, dur – sadafsiz” – “No rose without a thorn”; “Izlagan imkon topar” – “Where there is a will, there is a way”; “Don’t put off until tomorrow what you can do today” – “Bugungi ishni ertaga qo’yma”.

Conclusion Proverbs, generally, cover manyfold and widely diverse subjects being created by mankind over thousands of years that in them from the most complex problems of social life to the smallest traditions of family life, from moral norms of the family to the smallest flaws in the character of people, from the philosophical worldview to the characteristics of the smallest animals. As proverbs express the conclusion of many centuries of life experiences and constant daily observations in the form of a complete thought in a strict polarity, they are dominated by the diversity of meaning of each word, the stability of expressions, and the stability of form. However, depending on the place of use, their scope of meaning is constantly expanding. Therefore, their research as an object of scientific research from a linguistic and cultural point of view is still one of the urgent issues of linguistics.

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